

EQUITY, DIVERSITY, AND INCLUSION IN THE EUROPEAN ACADEMIES

SUMMARY

Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) in research ensures that all individuals, regardless of background, have fair access to resources, positions, and advancement in their careers. In addition, diversity of our research communities ensures that a wide range of perspectives and experiences are considered, it promotes creativity, and enhances the robustness and relevance of research outcomes. It is therefore not surprising that there is an increasing demand for transparency and good practice regarding the dimensions of equity, diversity and inclusion in the membership and research agenda of scientific institutions.

European academies of sciences and humanities play a pivotal role in enhancing EDI in research, as they are influential bodies in setting standards and guiding research policy. At the same time many academies do not accurately represent the scientific community and society, which risks leading to a decrease in societal and political trust and affecting their legitimacy and credibility as independent knowledge-brokers.

In this short report, the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA) assesses the different approaches to EDI currently in place within its membership. Based on a survey among ALLEA Member Academies, this report provides a qualitative overview of existing policies and initiatives, as well as a selection of established initiatives and recommendations that can directly be implemented by individual academies and umbrella organisations like ALLEA. This short report is intended to form a basis for dissemination and promotion of good practices and further in-depth monitoring of EDI within the European academies.

RECOMMENDATIONS TO EUROPEAN ACADEMIES

Based on the data received, recommendations to the European academies of sciences and humanities include to:

1. **embrace a broad approach to EDI**, considering diverse elements such as disability, discipline, ethnicity, geographic representation, language, socio-economic or cultural background, sexual orientation, religion, worldview, and more, extending beyond gender and age;
 2. **formalise their commitment** to EDI by incorporating it as a priority in their statutes or mission, and/or by endorsing a pledge to support EDI;
 3. **establish a clear timeline and specific measures** towards achieving EDI goals, taking into account their unique challenges and adhering to national laws and regulations;
 4. **develop and implement internal policies** addressing various aspects of EDI within their operations;
 5. **provide annual reports** on their EDI targets, progress, and activities, while also considering regular monitoring of diversity statistics across their activities;
 6. **engage with society** to promote equity, diversity, and inclusion by raising public awareness through actions like publishing research results, participating in education programs, advising policymakers and stakeholders, and collaborating with science communication experts;
- form a permanent committee or working group** focused on EDI.

RECOMMENDATIONS TO ALLEA

In addition, European umbrella organisations like ALLEA are recommended to:

1. **implement a working group on EDI**, which could take on the following activities:
 - provide a platform for member academies to discuss progress and challenges related to the above recommendations and promote sharing of innovative approaches to EDI;
 - organise an annual questionnaire survey to measure engagement with the topic in all member academies;
 - formulate core recommendations to inspire, improve, or complement existing approaches and activities of member academies;
 - share guiding examples of minimum requirements of measures and timelines;
 - assist, upon request, in establishing monitoring systems of yearly developments.
2. **develop an EDI strategy for ALLEA itself** to present to the General Assembly in 2025.
3. **collaborate with other European scientific institutions** and funding agencies to harmonise EDI actions.

STEERING GROUP

To oversee the collection and analysis of EDI data from among ALLEA's membership, a Steering Group was established, taking into consideration geography and gender balance, representation of senior and young academics, gender, and involving both academy fellows and senior-level staff members:

Name	Academy
Annette Grütters-Kieslich (Steering Group co-chair)	ALLEA Vice President – Leopoldina and Union of German Academies of Sciences and Humanities
Molly Morgan Jones (Steering Group co-chair)	British Academy
Achilles Emilianides	Academy of Cyprus
Marta Gmurek	Polish Academy of Sciences
Hani Harb	Junge Akademie
Kimberly Katte	Institute of Catalan Studies
Alla Kirova	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Pernilla Wittung-Stafshede	Royal Swedish Academy

EDI RESPONSES FROM ALLEA MEMBER ACADEMIES

ALLEA Member Academies were invited to submit their current EDI approaches, considering (but not limited to) the below categories:

- Existing policies and timelines to reach specific goals/outcomes
- Past and/or ongoing initiatives in the academy to support EDI
- Activities to promote awareness and change among fellowship and staff

The ALLEA Secretariat received 27 submissions from among its membership, including two notifying that no EDI approaches were in place.

Disclaimers to the data

- As many of the submissions contain internal policies and other confidential information, all data or recommendations are only presented or shared in an anonymised manner.
- To encourage the submission of a broad range of policies, recommendations, and actions, the steering group opted against requesting specific information or formats. As a result, it is at this stage not possible to draw any quantitative conclusions, because the absence of reporting from an academy regarding a particular activity does not necessarily imply inactivity in that area by the academy. For example, if an academy did not report any public engagement activities this could simply mean that they did not consider it relevant to report in this context.
- The EDI approach of several academies has been influenced by the demand of the European Commission to present a [gender equality plan \(GEP\)](#) when submitting funding proposals. As of 2022 and onwards, having a GEP has become a prerequisite for eligibility for participation in Horizon Europe funding calls for public bodies, higher education institutions, and research organisations from EU Member States and Associated Countries. Comparable activities of the EU Commission regarding other elements of EDI are currently lacking. This may have resulted in an overemphasis on reporting activities related to gender equality.
- The examples of practices from specific academies mentioned in the report are a selection made by the steering group and do not rely on a formal assessment or scoring system.

OVERVIEW OF ACADEMY APPROACHES TO EDI

The below table provides an overview of the different types of approaches to EDI that have been identified among ALLEA's membership, grouped in five categories. Whereas some approaches have been reported by multiple academies, others may have only been reported once – rather than providing a quantitative overview of the status quo, this table therefore intends to provide a resource for academies who seek inspiration for further approaches to improve EDI.

Policies & Guidelines
Formalising EDI as a priority in the academy's Statutes or Strategy
Developing policy documents aiming to increase representation in membership, governing bodies, and event speakers with diverse profiles and from diverse backgrounds
Creating internal guidelines for EDI-related themes such as gender-inclusive language, responsible debate, prevention of internal harassment, hiring/promotion*

Signalling the academy's commitment to EDI by being a member of international initiatives like the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), which emphasizes diversity and inclusiveness
Developing a gender equality plan (GEP) in compliance with Horizon Europe requirements
Reporting
Conducting diversity monitoring across the academy's activities
Establishing yearly diversity data reporting to members and society
Organisation
Appointing an EDI committee to address all issues and objectives related to equal treatment within the academy
Deploying a team of EDI professionals or an EDI advisor
Taking measures to achieve a diverse membership that is also reflected in governing bodies
Establishing a Young Academy or a centre dedicated to young researchers
Adopting 'blind' procedures to ensure fairer recruitment
Organising training sessions for staff to integrate EDI aspects into leadership courses, communication practices, etc.
Organising all-staff sessions to improve awareness and knowledge on various aspects of diversity
Establishing an internal mentoring programme focusing on the career development of young researchers and minority groups* at the academy
Events
Reviewing the accessibility of events and online content, and introduce EDI-related measures such as the use of automatic subtitling for video events
Providing childcare service to young researchers during events
Considering diversity of speakers and participants at events
Making events hybrid and provide (financial) support to underrepresented/disadvantaged groups to facilitate participation for everyone*
Research and funding activities
Dedicating funding to research(ers) on topics related to EDI in science and broader social contexts
Establishing grant programmes supporting researchers with diverse profiles and from diverse backgrounds, both within and outside of the academy
Societal awareness & Policy advice
Organising public lectures and other events on EDI to improve public awareness
Publishing EDI-themed books, articles, podcasts, and other publications
Creating educational activities for all ages, from high school to PhD students
Making suggestions for government research policy highlighting the need for diversity within the research landscape

The measures indicated with an asterisk () were not part of the submissions but are endorsed by the Steering Group*

RESOURCES OF ESTABLISHED INITIATIVES

The below overview comprises a selection of established initiatives identified within ALLEA's membership and is not intended to provide an exhaustive list of all measures taken at ALLEA Member Academies. Only publicly available resources are listed:

Policies, guidelines, action plans

- The Union of the German Academies of Sciences and Humanities has a [Guideline on Diversity and Equal Opportunity](#), which has been signed by all member academies. Diversity has been recognised as a [strategic priority](#) by the British Academy in its Strategic Plan 2018-2022, while the Learned Society of Wales published a [Diversity, Equity and Inclusion \(DEI\) Statement](#).
- The Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences has released the [Agenda for Diversity & Inclusion 2022-2025 Plan](#) to meet the gender equality requirements of Horizon Europe.
- The Young Academy of Scotland has introduced the [Charter for Responsible Debate](#), promoting constructive dialogue on contentious issues with a strong emphasis on inclusivity and equity.
- The Austrian Academy of Sciences and the Institute of Catalan Studies have both established guidelines on gender-inclusive language (available only in [German](#) and [Catalan](#).)
- The [Gender Equality in Academia and Research \(GEAR\) tool](#), co-developed by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) and the European Commission's Directorate General for Research and Innovation, provides practical advice and tools for setting up a gender equality plan and for its evaluation.
- Science Europe's '[Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments](#)' highlights key findings from a membership survey conducted in 2023, showcases good practices, and provides practical recommendations across topics such as positive action measures and the collection and use of diversity data.

Actions related to the academy's own operations

- The Royal Society's diversity committee regularly monitors diversity statistics across the Society's activities and publishes an [annual data report](#).
- The British Academy has reviewed the accessibility of its events and website, introduced automatic subtitling for video events, and offers [accessibility-related information](#) for visitors on its website.
- The Young Academy of Scotland is committed to recruiting [At-Risk Academics and Refugee \(ARAR\)](#) professionals as members.
- The British Academy has adopted 'blind' recruitment procedures as its primary hiring process, utilising [Applied](#), a recruitment platform that reduces bias and ensures fairer recruitment.
- The [Career Development Fellowship](#) of the Royal Society, a four-year, postdoctoral research fellowship, aims to support the retention of researchers from underrepresented backgrounds in STEM fields. The Lincoi Academy has initiated a [scholarship programme](#) to support Ukrainian researchers, while several ALLEA Member Academies participate in the [L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science national and regional Young Talents Programmes](#).

- Through the [Robertson Trust Mentoring Scheme](#), the Young Academy of Scotland offers mentoring opportunities to undergraduate scholars who encounter barriers to higher education.

Outreach

- The Hungarian Academy of Sciences published a [book](#) and the Institute of Catalan Studies hosts a [podcast](#) as part of their outreach activities, both focusing on women in science.
- Commissioned by the Royal Society, [National Life Stories at the British Library](#) undertook an oral history project, interviewing scientists from a variety of educational and minority ethnic backgrounds.

ABOUT ALLEA

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing nearly 60 academies from about 40 EU and non-EU countries. Since its foundation in 1994, ALLEA speaks out on behalf of its members on European and international stages, promotes science as a global public good, and facilitates scientific collaboration across borders and disciplines. Learn more here: www.allea.org.

Citation: For citation purposes, please use the following: ALLEA (2024). “Equality, Diversity, and Inclusivity in European Academies”. DOI: 10.26356/EDI

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